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NWAFOR ORIZU COLLEGE OF EDUCATION,
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NWAFOR ORIZU COLLEGE OF EDUCATION
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(cgbebonss@gmail.com)

List of Contributors

Dr. Amaka B. Chiakwelu

Department of Mathematics
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State
Email: amakachiakwelu@gmail.com
08038995271

Dr. Njide F. Okeke

Department of Mathematics
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State
E-mail: njidejisuus@yahoo.com 08036134373

Dr. Anthonia Chinyere Uwa

Department of Human Kinetics and Health
Education, Nwafor Orizu College of
Education, Nsugbe, Anambra State
E-mail: Uwa.anthonia@yahoo.com
08035764833

Paschal Ezekwesili Achugbu

Department of Human Kinetics and Health
Education, Nwafor Orizu College of
Education, Nsugbe, Anambra State
08037569132

Dr. P. I. I. Ikokwu

Department of Chemistry, School of Sciences
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State
ikeikokwu@yahoo.com 08068686868

Franklin N. Ibe

Department of Chemistry, School of Sciences
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State
nnannafranklin@yahoo.com 08133900848

Dr. Ekene N. Igboegwu

Department of Chemistry
Nwafor Orizu College of Education

Nsugbe, Anambra State

E-mail: igboegwuekene@gmail.com
08064552325

Chiemeka A. Udegbonam

Department of Chemistry
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State
E-mail: udegbonamchiemeka@gmail.com
08037644064

Dr. Jane N. Achufusi

Department of Biology
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State
08023163803

Clement C. Okpala

Department of Biology
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State
08065979288

Ruffina N. Adimonyemma

Department of Biology
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State
08033208400

Philomina Obianuju Nweke

Department of Physics
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State
E-mail: philominaobianujunweke@gmail.com
07080424299

Sabina Chizoba Obiadazie

Department of Physics
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State

E-mail: chezlivventures@yahoo.com
08030663004

Dr. Chika Gertrude Nwachukwu
Department of Human Kinetics And Health
Education, Nwafor Orizu College of
Education, Nsugbe, Anambra State
08033231398

Dr. Nkechi Eucharika Ibeagha
Department of Human Kinetics And Health
Education, Nwafor Orizu College of
Education, Nsugbe, Anambra State
08039328983

Dr. Julie Nuoli
Department of Chemistry
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State
E-mail: nkejul@yahoo.com
08036736987

Dr. Mary-Ann E. Udogu
Department of Chemistry
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
P M B 1734 Nsugbe, Anambra State
E-mail: maryannebele2013@gmail.com
08063931181

Dr. Anastasia O. Udoh
Department of Physics
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State.
E-mail: udohanastasia@gmail.com
08035531753

Dr. Nnamdi B. Emendu
Department of Chemistry
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State, Nigeria.
E-mail: nnamdiemendu@gmail.com
08036681472

Faith Nneka Ojobo
Department of Chemistry
Nwafor Orizu College of Education

Nsugbe, Anambra State, Nigeria
E-mail: valentinaney@gmail.com
08100245148

Ifeoma Orakwue
Department of Chemistry
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State, Nigeria
E-mail: ifeomagoods@gmail.com
08161511461

Ebele R. Emendu
Department of Geography and Meteorology
Nnamdi Azikiwe University
Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria
E-mail: emenduebele@gmail.com
08037596515

Dr. Charles C. Chukwurah
Department of Mathematics
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State

Obiageli R. Ofodu
Army Day Secondary School
Onitsha, Anambra State
Nigeria

Okonkwo, Perpetua
Department of Physics
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State
Email: peepyy@yahoo.com
+234-8035074423

Chuka Charles Onukwuba
Department of Mathematics
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State
E-mail: stonukwubacharles@gmail.com
08033913281

Eucharika U. Obidigbo
Department of Mathematics
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State

Onyinye Chienyem Okeke
Department of Integrated Science
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State
E-mail: trendyzonyii@gmail.com
0806 259 8497

Onyeka Michael Ikele
Department of Microbiology
Nnamdi Azikiwe University
Awka, Anambra State
E-mail: mo.ikele@unizik.edu.ng
0806 168 7898

Eucharía U. Obidigbo
Department of Mathematics
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe,
E-mail: Eucharíaobidigbo@gmail.com
07031559942

Jireh C. Udeze
Department of Physics
Nwafor Orizu College of Education,
Nsugbe, Anambra State

Ifeanýi Cyprian Nnanyelugo
Department of Physics
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State
Nnanyelugocyprianifeanyi@gmail.com
08064958007

Philomena Ndidí Ike
Department of Physics
Nwafor Orizu college of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State Nigeria
E-mail: ndidiokoyephil@gmail.com
08067586997

Emmanuel Izuchukwu Ofoegbunam
Department of Computer Science
Federal School of Surveying
Oyo, Oyo State Nigeria
Ofoegbunam1@gmail.com
0803 893 5058

Dr. Wilson Obinna Igbasi
Computer Science Department
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State
Email: signor.wilson4study@gmail.com

Chioma P. Ifeanyi-Obiorah
Department of Mathematics
Nwafor Orizu College of Education
Nsugbe, Anambra State
Email: obipeace71@gmail.com
08068601852

Dr. Edith Nkiru Obande-Ogbuinya
Department of Physical and Health
Education, Alex Ekwueme University
Ndufu-Alike, Ebonyí State

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Entrepreneurial Skills for Innovative Chemistry Education: A Panacea for Achieving Nigeria's Sustainable Development

By

Dr. Julie Nnoli¹

And

Dr. Mary-Ann E. Udogu²

Department of Chemistry

Nwafor Orizu College of Education,

P M B 1734 Nsugbe, Anambra State

e-mail: nkejul@yahoo.com 08036736987

²e-mail: maryannebele2013@gmail.com 08063931181

Abstract

This paper discussed the entrepreneurial skills involved in Chemistry education which students can venture into on graduation as innovative science and technology. These initiatives would be a panacea for achieving Nigeria's sustainable development. Chemistry which most students consider as volatile and abstract can be made concrete to students when some practices that are enshrined in Chemistry education curricular are utilized properly by the teachers and as such give room for the acquisition of entrepreneurial skills. The procedures for the production of wine through fermentation method, air-refreshner and disinfectants were presented in this write-up. It was recommended that students should be encouraged to develop the ability to control one's own life, apply problem solving, creativity and interpersonal communication in Chemistry. This paper also proffered solutions which if utilized by Chemistry teachers would assist in ameliorating the predicaments in educational system and help learners develop skills, for sustainable development of the entire nation.

Keywords: *Innovative, Science, Technology, Panacea, Sustainable Development, Entrepreneurial skills.*

Introduction

Sustainable development is used in a variety of contexts and with different connotations which are most often not made explicit. In particular, it is frequently used with reference to just one aspect, namely the education and training of scholars (Malcom, Cetto, Dickson, Gaillard, Schaeffer and Quere, 2002). Osioma (2011) pointed out that in addition to challenges of

appropriate curricular content needed to support ideas of sustainability and inadequate infrastructure for instruction, expressed that "perhaps the greatest challenge for providing authentic forms of learning and teaching in science is in the capacity of teachers for sustainable development". Most have not been educated in ways that reinforce hands on inquiry based approaches to instruction or incorporation

of topics from local contexts that may require an interdisciplinary focus. Okeke (2012), is of the view that the final step in sustainable development is the ability of a nation, a state or people to engage creatively in science education, scientific research, the development of new technologies and their applications to economic, social and human needs.

According to Eniayeju (2010), STM means Science, Technology and Mathematics. Science according to Nnoli (2019), is the intellectual and practical activity encompassing the systematic study of the structure and behavior of the physical and natural world through observation and experiment. Nnoli (2019) further maintained that science is also a systematic enterprise that builds and organizes knowledge in the form of testable explanations and predictions about the universe. Uko (2007), states that science process is an ability which can be developed through real experience in carrying out mental operations and physical activities. The process of science is the foundation for scientific behavior which can be acquired by students to do what scientists do. The scientific method, scientific thinking, critical thinking, scientific attitudes are terms used to describe these science process skills. Example: observing, classifying, measuring, inferring, predicting, communicating and so on. Scientific method is defined as the procedures through which facts that make up the body of knowledge have been discovered. The procedures includes the following: Making observations, identifying a problem, formulating hypothesis, designing experiment, conducting experiment, analyzing the result, drawing conclusion, share findings, accept hypothesis and propose theories. Uko (2007), defines technology as the application of scientific knowledge for practical purposes, especially in industry. He says that it is also the collection of techniques, skills, methods and processes used in the production of goods and

services or in accomplishment of the objectives, such as in scientific investigation. Mathematics according to Eniayeju (2010), is the study of topics such as quantity, numbers, structures, space and change. Mathematics is used to model natural and artificial experiments in order to identify problems and develop a solutions for them. The burden of evidence from the qualitative study reported here on STM attributions, that is, what students perceive as the causes of their performances in STM shows that students attribute underachievement in STM to the ways STM courses are taught. This measure of inadequacy on the part of STM teachers calls for interventions of methodologies especially in the area of teacher preparation. According to him, two of such interventions are contextualization of STM education and adoption of authentic formative assessment approaches. Many concepts in STM are abstract by nature thereby making their learning relatively difficult when compared with some other non-STM concepts although the resourcefulness and effectiveness of the teacher is paramount in conquering the so called "difficult barriers".

Chemistry is one of the most important branches of science which enables learners to understand what happen around them. It helps them to solve simple problems they encounter daily. Hence Udogu (2009), stated that the most interesting aspect of Chemistry is that it applies to our daily lives. According to Nnoli (2021), chemistry is a discipline which high standard of conduct must be applied by teachers and researches in ways that students cannot fail to observe and adopt. The complexity of the task is such that one can no longer easily acquire the necessary skills without some formal instructions which play a critical role on what students learn in the Chemistry classrooms. Chemistry has helped so many people in acquisition of entrepreneurial skills for self employment, especially this time we have

scarcity of jobs due to socio-economic problems. The skills acquired in chemistry do not require any funding from abroad as their capital requirements are often moderate. Such skills are important because, in keeping with the principle of comparative advantage, they make use of available natural/human resources for maximum output and sustainable development (Newbury, 2001).

Azuka (2003) defined entrepreneurs as innovators who use scientific, technological and business processes to change the status quo or the existing products and services to set up new products and services. Entrepreneurship development according to Mueller (2004) is the process of improving the skills and knowledge of entrepreneurs through various training and classroom programs. Entrepreneurship is regarded traditionally as an ability and willingness to enhance, hold and manage a business venture while being prepared for taking risks to get the highest profit. The modern trends see entrepreneurship as the world transformation by means of solving its most significant problems by identification of business opportunities through innovative views and creativity. Entrepreneurial skills are acquired by a person that has interest and high need to improve his or her skills and knowledge. He is visionary, purposeful, energetic and a risk taker. A set of experienced entrepreneurs is a must-have for the economy and industry of any country. That is why countries all over the world encourage participation and investments to be able to compete within business levels.

In Chemistry, there are many manufacturing activities requiring entrepreneurial skills for capacity building. Some of these will be discussed in this paper as presented in the following paragraphs.

1. Production of wine through fermentation method of absolute alcohol (ethanol)
2. Production of air refreshner.
3. Production of disinfectants

Production of wine from ethanol (Absolute alcohol)

Materials for the production of ethanol. These include:

Grape, Juice extractor, water, a cork bottle, knife, a sieve and a bowl

Ethanol has the molecular formula of C_2H_5OH . It is a very important compound because it has more uses than almost any other organic compound. It is the essential ingredient in alcoholic drinks and is well-known for its intoxicating effect on its consumers. It is a colorless, volatile liquid with a characteristic taste and smell. It can burn in air with a pale blue flame to yield water and carbon dioxide. It reacts with acid to form esters.

Procedure

This is produced by the process of fermentation. Fermentation is the slow decomposition or biodegradation of large organic molecules (such as starch) into smaller molecules such as ethanol by micro-organisms (eg: bacteria). Grape is crushed and allowed to ferment for two days. In wine making, grapes are the sources of sugars and yeast. As grapes ripen, the amount of sugar inside them increases and yeast grows on the outer skin which will enhance the fermentation. By crushing the grape, the sugary juice and yeast are brought into contact and then fermentation starts. After two days, filter and keep as your ethanol.

Uses

1. Ethanol is a good solvent. It is used in paints, vanishes, polishes, soaps, perfumes, dyes, drugs etc.
2. Manufacture of many important products e.g ethanol, ethyl esters
3. As fuel, either by itself or mixed with petrol to improve octane rating.
4. As an anti-freeze in automobile radiators
5. In alcoholic drinks e.g beers, wine, spirits etc.

Production of wine

Materials for the production of wine

Grape, Juice extractor, water, a cork bottle, knife, a sieve, a bowl, One cup of zobo and pineapple or banana flavor.

If you want to produce wine, collect one cup of zobo leaves, cook for five minutes, filter and keep. Mix both ethanol and zobo, add pineapple or banana flavor and serve as wine.

Air-refreshener

Materials for the production of air refreshener.

Ethanol – as a solvent

Perfume – for nice fragrance

Texapon – as antiseptic (kills bacteria)

Camphor -- as preservative

Procedure

Dissolve 1/4 litre of perfume in a 1/2 litre of ethanol and pour into a 1/4 litre of texapon. Add preservative. Your air- refreshener is ready for use.

Disinfectants

Materials for Disinfectants:

Ethanol - as a solvent

Pine oil - as anticeptic and aroma

Texapon gel – as a foaming agent

Chloroxylnol - as anticeptic

Colour – as good appearance

Water – major solvent (gives homogeneous mixture)

Procedure

Put 0.5kg of texapon gel inside a bowl and dissolve with 1/2 a litre of ethanol. Add one tea cup of water to make it homogeneous. Add 1/4 litre of pine oil and stir. Then add 1/4 litre of chloroxylnol and stir vigorously to get a clear solution. Add colour little by little in order to know when it changes. Texapon gel or Sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS) makes disinfectants to foam and chloroxylnol brings a white colour when disinfectants is dropped into water.

Summary

Chemistry education is a complex and highly skilled endeavour. It is a discovery process which requires practices that give room for the acquisition of scientific skills and industrial processes which make science concrete. These process skills can be applied into independent business ventures. Different entrepreneurial skills have been explored in this write-up. This should be properly integrated into the science curriculum at various levels in order to produce more functional graduates. The acquisition of these skills will help unemployed graduates to set up business of their own as a means of livelihood. Acquiring these skills may also be of benefit to those who may not be able to make it to tertiary institutions. It may even serve as a means of making extra income for those who are already employed. This will guarantee a future for the youths and create a peaceful and prosperous society.

Conclusion

The writer is of the opinion that chemistry is a volatile and abstract subject and can be made concrete to students when some practices that are enshrined in chemistry education are utilized properly by the chemistry teachers and give room for the acquisition of entrepreneurial skills. Secondly, if all the solutions proffered in this paper are utilized by chemistry teachers, it would help in ameliorating the predicaments in educational system and help learners develop skills, for capacity building.

Recommendations

1. Government should create the enabling environment for innovation and enterprise to thrive so that the economy can be production-driven to encourage mass production of science graduate generally, as there will be capacity to absorb them.
2. Teachers should develop science process skills in such a way that the learner will be

able to demonstrate them at the end of instruction and utilize them in future.

3. Besides, primary and secondary education forms the bedrocks for knowledge and skills acquisition. This entrepreneurial skills should therefore be integrated into science contents that will give the people sense of purpose and direction in life.
4. Professional development of the science teachers should be encouraged in order to keep the teachers abreast of the current issues in education and help them refine their professional practice with a focus on skills development.
5. Chemistry teaching method should be modernized to bring life back to Chemistry classrooms.
6. Locally made products should be financed and patronized in order to encourage the

productions of larger quantities.

7. Well equipped laboratories should be provided in schools as well as laboratory assistants/technologist for effective chemistry education.
8. Chemistry teachers should be encouraged to attend workshops, seminars and conferences for professional growth. They should also make the teaching and learning processes to be activity-based to help the students develop skills for self-sustainability.
9. More qualified chemistry teachers should be employed to provide for adequate manpower.
10. In developing Chemistry curricula, the needs of students and the society at large should be considered.

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